

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№3 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2022-3>

Бош мухаррир:

Холбеков Муҳаммаджон

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:

Тўхтасинов Илҳом

ф.ф.д., доцент (Ўзбекистон)

Главный редактор:

Холбеков Муҳаммаджон

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Тухтасинов Илҳом

к.ф.н., доцент (Ўзбекистон)

Editor in Chief:

Kholbekov Muhammadjan

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

Tuhtasinov Ilhom

Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Uzbekistan)

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли

ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким

ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил

ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт

Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддиқова Ирода

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар

ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек

масбул котиб, доцент (Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умар оғли

д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бокиева Гуландом

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким

д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил

д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Джеймс Форт

Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддиқова Ирода

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар

д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек

отв. секретарь, доцент (Ўзбекистон)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov

academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed

Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort

University of Michigan (USA)

Umardhodjaev Mukhtar

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar

Doc. of philol. sci. (Georgia)

Yusupov Oybek

Ass. prof. (Uzbekistan) - Senior Secretary

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Sharipov S.S. ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЯ (ТАРЖИМА ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЯСИ) РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИНГ АСОСИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ.....	5
2. Akhadova Guzal Imatulloevna, Mavlyanova Nilufar Suvankulovna METHODOLOGY AND PRINCIPLES OF USING ROLE PLAYING IN FOREIGN LESSONS.....	12
3. Atayeva Khusniya Kurashevna, Fayziyeva Yulduz Yusupovna USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND TEACHING METHODS AT THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSON.....	17
4. Absamatova Gulhayo Bakhodirovna LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF SIGN LANGUAGE AUTOMATIZATION.....	24
5. Shuhratova Visola jamshid qizi KAZUO ISHIGURONING "DAFN ETILGAN GIGANT"ASARIDAGI KONSEPTLAR UYG'UNLIGI.....	30
6. Bazarova Shahlo Shuxratovna KOREYS ADIBASI SHIN KYON SUK IJODINING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI XUSUSIDA.....	36
7. Kasimova Adiba Nasirovna TRANSLATION METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF PUBLICISTIC MATERIALS.....	41
8. Арзикулова Хуршида Акабаралиевна “ГОРАЦИЙ” ТРАГЕДИЯСИДА ИНСОНИЙ ФАЗИЛАТЛАР ВА ОИЛАВИЙ БУРЧ.....	47
9. Mamadjanova Nargiza Mahmudjanovna ZAMONAVIY INGLIZ TILIDA MUROJAATNING KOMMUNIKATIV FUNKSIYASI.....	52
10. Икромова Нигина ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТЕКСТА (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯ Ч.АЙТМАТОВА “ПРОЩАЙ, ГУЛЬСАРИ!”).....	58
11. Абдусаматов Зафарбек Нурмат ўғли ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИДА АНТРОПОНИМЛАР ТУРИ ВА ИФОДА ШАКЛЛАРИ.....	65
12. Abduraxmonova Nilufar Zaynobbiddin qizi, Vosiljonov Azizbek Boxodirjon o'g'li O'ZBEK TILI ELEKTRON KORPUSIDA DIALEKTAL KORPUS YARATISHNING NAZARIY MASALALARI.....	70
13. Achilova Noila Hamroqulovna SUYUQLIK MIQDORINI ANGLATUVCHI LISONIY BIRLIKLARNING PRAGMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	75
14. Tadjibayeva Gulzoda ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKDA ANTROPOTSENTRIK PARADIGMA.....	81
15. Begimqulova Dilobar INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA REDUPLIKATIVLIKNING MORFOLOGIK IFODALANISHINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	86
16. Amonova Zilola Qodirovna, Axrorova Zufnunabegim Rizvonovna HUSAYNIYNING BADIY MAHORATI.....	93

17. Наргиза Жахонова ТАВТОЛОГИЯ ВА ПЛЕОНАЗМНИНГ ЎРГАНИЛИШ ТАРИХИГА БИР НАЗАР.....	99
18. O`dayeva Shahnoza Shuxratovna</b> RANG, MAZA-TA`M MA`NOSINI ANGLATUVCHI LISONIY BIRLIKLARNING PRAGMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	105
19. Gaybullayeva Malokhat Pulatovna HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH DIALECTS.....	111
20. Xamrayeva Zebiniso Xaydar qizi QO`SHMA GAPNING STRUKTUR – SEMANTIK TAHLILI (INGLIZ TILI ASOSIDA).....	116
21. Umaraliev Dildora Takhirjanovna PECULIARITIES OF LEGAL TERMS.....	122
22. Дилноза Раматжановна Рузматова ХОЛИД ҲОСИЙНИЙ АСАРЛАРИДА АФҒОНИСТОН ПЕРСПЕКТИВАСИ: ТАРИХИЙ ВА БАДИИЙ ТАЛҚИН.....	128
23. Sodiqova Yulduz Furqatovna LITERARY TEXT AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTIC RESEARCH AND THE PROBLEM OF ITS INTERPRETATION.....	134
24. Bozorbekov A. LOGISTIKA TERMINOLOGIYA TIZIMINING XUSUSIYATLARI.....	138
25. Ulikova Mavluda CRITERIA FOR THE SELECTION OF TERMS DENOTING FAMILY TIES.....	144
26. Воситов Валижон Абдувахобович ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДА ТУРКИЗМЛАРНИНГ ПАЙДО БЎЛИШ САБАБЛАРИ.....	150
27. Холибекова Омонгул Кенжабоевна ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДАГИ АЛЛЮЗИВ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИК БИРЛИКЛАР ТАЛҚИНИ.....	155
28. Дилбар Холтемировна Ниязова ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИДА ЛИСОНИЙ ШАХС ТИПЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШГА ХИЗМАТ ҚИЛУВЧИ МАХСУС БИРЛИКЛАР.....	160
29. Шамахмудова Азиза Фуркатовна ҲУРМАТ ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИНИНГ ГЕНДЕР АСПЕКТЛАРИ.....	167
30. Azimov Abdikhamidullo Xolmanovich TO'PLAM IBODATLAR TURLARI VA ULARNING TASNIFI PRINSIPLARI.....	173
31. Boboyev Temur Mahmadmurodovich ROLE OF SHORT HUMOROUS POEMS IN DIFFERENT CULTURAL BACKGROUNDS...	178
32. Ж.О. Каниязова Ш.СЕЙТОВТЫҢ «ЖАМАНШЫҒАНАҚТАҒЫ АҚТУБА» ҲӘМ Ш.ХАЛМЫРЗАЕВТЫҢ “ОЛАБЎЖИ” РОМАНЛАРЫНДА ТУБАЛАЎШЫЛЫҚ ДӘЎИРИНИҢ СУЎРЕТЛЕНИЎИ.....	184
33. Shukurov Foziljon Mahmadvovich TEMURIYLAR DAVRI SHOIRI - BISOTIY SAMARQANDIY G`AZALLARINING POETIKASIDA YANGILIKLAR.....	192

ISSN: 2181-9297

www.tadqiqot.uz

Akhadova Guzal Imatulloevna,Senior teacher of the Department of Foreign Languages,
Samarkand State Architectural and Civil Engineering Institute**Mavlyanova Nilufar Suvankulovna,**Teacher of the Department of Foreign Languages,
Samarkand State Architectural and Civil Engineering Institute

METHODOLOGY AND PRINCIPLES OF USING ROLE PLAYING IN FOREIGN LESSONS

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6637766>

ANNOTATION

This article focuses on the main features of interactive lessons. Knowledge of a foreign language is becoming a necessary part of a person's personal and professional life in modern society. There is a need for a large number of citizens to have practical knowledge of one or more foreign languages and, in this regard, to get real chances to occupy a more prestigious position in society, both socially and financially. From this it is clear that the social order of society in relation to foreign languages in connection with the presence of a real access to a different culture and its representative is expressed not only in practical knowledge of the language, but also in the ability to use this language in real communication. The new socio-economic and political situation causes an increase in the requirements for the level of language training of students of all categories.

Keywords: principle of humanization, principle of unity, principle of consciousness, principles, activity, preparatory stage, independent work, communication motives, cognitive motives.

Ахадова Гузаль Иматуллоевна,Самаркандский государственный архитектурно-строительный институт,
старший преподаватель кафедры иностранных языков**Мавлянова Нилуфар Суванкуловна,**преподаватель кафедры иностранных языков
Самаркандский государственный архитектурно-строительный институт

МЕТОДИКА И ПРИНЦИПЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ РОЛЕВЫХ ИГР НА УРОКАХ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Знание иностранного языка становится в современном обществе необходимой частью личной и профессиональной жизни человека. Возникает потребность большого количества граждан, в практическом владении одним или несколькими иностранными языками и получить в связи с этим реальные шансы занять в обществе более престижное, как социальное, так и материальное отношения положение. Отсюда ясно, что социальный заказ общества по отношению к иностранным языкам в связи с наличием реального выхода на иную культуру и

ее представителя выражается не только в практическом знании языка, но и в умении использовать этот язык в реальной коммуникации. Новая социально-экономическая и политическая ситуация обуславливает повышение требования к уровню языковой подготовки обучаемых всех категорий.

Ключевые слова: принцип гуманизации, принцип единства, принцип сознательности, принципы, активность, подготовительный этап, самостоятельной работа, мотивы общения, познавательные мотивы.

Axadova Guzal Imatulloevna,
Samarqand davlat arxitektura-qurilish instituti,
Xorijiy tillar kafedrasida katta o'qituvchisi
Mavlyanova Nilufar Suvanqulovna,
Xorijiy tillari kafedrasida o'qituvchisi,
Samarqand davlat arxitektura-qurilish instituti

CHET DARSLARIDA ROLLI O'YINLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI VA PRINSIPLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqola interaktiv usulda o'tiladigan darslarning asosiy xususiyatlariga bag'ishlanadi Xorijiy tilni bilish zamonaviy jamiyatda insonning shaxsiy va kasbiy hayotining zaruriy qismiga aylanib bormoqda. Fuqarolarning katta qismi bir yoki bir nechta xorijiy tillarni amaliy bilishi va shu munosabat bilan jamiyatda ham ijtimoiy, ham moliyaviy jihatdan obro'lroq mavqeni egallash uchun real imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lishi zarur. Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, jamiyatning chet tillariga nisbatan ijtimoiy tartibi boshqa madaniyat va uning vakiliga real kirish imkoniyati mavjudligi bilan bog'liq holda nafaqat tilni amaliy bilishda, balki tilni bilish qobiliyatida ham namoyon bo'ladi. haqiqiy muloqotda bu tildan foydalanish. Yangi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va siyosiy vaziyat barcha toifadagi talabalarning tilni tayyorlash darajasiga qo'yiladigan talablarning oshishiga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: insonparvarlik tamoyili, birlik tamoyili, ong printsiplari, tamoyillar, faoliyat, tayyorgarlik bosqichi, mustaqil ish, muloqot motivlari, kognitiv motivlar.

Under the conditions of language acquisition in an artificial language environment, a person compares the language experience he has acquired with the experience in his native language. G.A. Kitaygorodskaya argues that role-playing is more appropriate in this case. Actually, the study of a language lies not in the field of consciousness or intuition, but in the way of assimilating language rules. It is necessary to teach children a foreign language not only with the help of special tasks and exercises, since this only leads to the formation of reproductive skills in students, but it is imperative to introduce gaming technologies, which increases the effectiveness of learning. Teaching foreign language speaking with the help of role-playing games will allow the student to adequately navigate in a communicative situation, that is, to play the role of a real component within a particular communication to one degree or another. This is the relevance of the experiment. To achieve this goal, a set of role-playing games was introduced into the educational process. This complex of role-playing games was created for students of the fifth and sixth grades. This set of role-playing games was created taking into account the English language curriculum for the sixth grade and is based on the material of the New millennium English textbook, author N.N. Derevianko.

L.V. Markhadaev gives the following definition of a complex: a "complex" is a set of mental formations (motives, interests, attitudes) united by a single effect, which usually operates at an unconscious level, but determines the direction and structure of a person's conscious life [2, 25].

That is why the role-playing games we have selected are a complex, since they are united by a single goal - the development of communication skills, the ability of students to speak a foreign language in English lessons, on the topics studied:

1. "Keep fit and healthy."

2. "At a department store (Clothes)".

3. At the restaurant..

For the successful implementation of the set of role-playing games we have created, the following conditions must be taken into account:

- 1) observe the unity and goals, content, methods, forms and means of education;
- 2) take into account the age characteristics of students;
- 3) include all students (as far as possible) in game activities;
- 4) follow the methodology for conducting role-playing games in English lessons (rules, stages, inclusion of all structural components);
- 5) observe general pedagogical, psychological and subject-specific principles;
- 6) use a personality-oriented approach (taking into account interests, types of temperament, needs of students. For example, this is especially important at the stage of distribution of roles) [5, 137].

When creating a complex of role-playing games, the following principles were taken into account, which allow creating optimal conditions for self-realization of students, contributing to a favorable psychological climate in the classroom, allowing to take into account age and individual characteristics:

General - pedagogical principles:

- the principle of humanization (the use of role-playing in the classroom allows you to develop the independence of students, establish sincere and friendly relations between children);
- the principle of unity of the individual and the collective beginning (role-playing game allows you to create conditions for the full development of the child's personality in a team);

Didactic principles:

- the principle of consciousness (previously for each game we carry out some preparation, and then the game itself);
- the principle of activity (observance of the speech activity of students in the lesson);
- the principle of visibility (use of pictures, handouts);
- the principle of accessibility and feasibility (all material is offered to students, taking into account the curriculum and age characteristics of students; the number of lexical units and statements corresponds to the norms and requirements of the State Educational Standard in a foreign language);

Private methodological principles:

- the principle of communication (in a role-playing game, everyone has the right to express their own opinion. It also allows you to motivate students to learn the language.)
- the principle of oral advance (oral introduction and consolidation of the material is used; the role-playing game itself involves oral communication);
- the principle of taking into account the native language (students receive homework, thereby preparing to participate in a role-playing game, which ensures the prevention of possible errors);

Psychological principles:

- the principle of the stage-by-stage formation of speech actions (role-playing games will be held according to the stages of implementation. Galskova N.D. identifies the following stages: a) preparatory stage; b) holding the game; c) control)
- the principle of taking into account the individual mental characteristics of students (teenage students are characterized by increased sociability, which is important when organizing pair and group communication, and conducting role-playing games. The game contributes to the development of logical thinking, reinforces the tendency to reasoning.

When introducing a complex of role-playing games, it is advisable to use the following methods [6,37]:

- interactive method (students work in small groups, pairs);
- visual: illustration method (use of visualization: pictures, handouts, toys);
- practical (use of training exercises);
- the method of independent work of students (work with a book, written assignments);
- communicative method (role-play encourages students to communicate),

It should also be noted that the use of a complex of role-playing games contributes to the development of motives, such as:

- 1) motives for communication;
- 2) moral motives;
- 3) cognitive motives.

We will use the following psychological techniques that help increase students' motivation for learning activities [1,20]:

- use of cards with metered help;
- encouragement (praise, encouragement);
- creating a situation of success;
- Giving help;
- conducting a collective discussion of the results of the work.

Working with a complex of role-playing games, we will adhere to the stages of conducting role-playing games in this article.

Introducing a complex of role-playing games into the educational process, the rules for conducting role-playing games developed by E.A. Maslyko, which made it possible to organize the activities of students [3,35]:

- 1) Students must put themselves in a situation in which everything outside the classroom can be in real life.
- 2) Learners need to adapt to a certain role in a similar situation. In some cases he may play himself, in others he will have to take on an imaginary role.
- 3) Participants in the role-playing game need to behave as if everything that happens is happening in real life; their behavior should be appropriate to the role they play.
- 4) Participants in the game should focus on the communicative use of language units, and not on the usual practice of fixing their speech [3, 26].

This complex was developed taking into account the methodology of using a role-playing game, i.e. according to the stages, methods, principles, rules and recommendations for this type of games.

At the stage of assimilation, a controlled type of role-playing games is used. Here, role-playing games are reproductive in nature. The work is based on an example of a sample that you can use. The consolidation phase uses moderately controlled role play. Now the activity is productive. And at the control stage, a free role-playing game is presented, which allows you to apply the knowledge of students in dialogic speech.

Thus, taking into account all the conditions, rules, attitudes, methods, techniques, principles, the complex of role-playing games developed by us will effectively increase the level of formation of skills, communication skills, and speaking of students.

In conclusion, game technologies represent a deep pedagogical value, it is a sphere of communication in which the student reveals himself, his development and education takes place; it motivates and encourages action. Using the game teaching method, we solve important methodological problems such as: the psychological readiness of students to communicate; repeated repetition of language material; training students in choosing the right speech option. Another important advantage of it is that it can be used as a lesson, part of the lesson, or as an element of extracurricular activities.

Used literature

1. Зимняя И. А. Психологические аспекты обучения говорению на иностранном языке / И. А. Зимняя. – М.: Наука, 1987. – 69 с.
2. Мархадаев Л. В. Словарь по социальной педагогике / Л. В. Мархадаев. – М.: Академия, 2002. – 368 с.
3. Маслыка Е. А., Бабинская П. К. Настольная книга преподавателя иностранного языка: справочное пособие. – М.: Высшая школа, 2001. – 538 с.

4. Маркова С.М., Наркозиёв А.К. Методика исследования содержания профессионального образования // Вестник Мининского университета. 2019. Т. 7, №1. С 2.
5. Назарова Н. А. Овладение иностранным языком в школе
6. Н. А. Назарова // Высшее образование в России. – 1999. – №6, – С. 73–76.
7. Осечкин В. В. Популярный энциклопедический иллюстрированный словарь / В. В. Осечкин. – М.: ОЛМА-ПРЕСС, 2003. – 1168 с.
8. Хегболдт П. Изучение иностранных языков: Пер. с англ. – М.: Наука, 1963. – 250 с.
9. Типологии уроков, методов и приемов обучения [Электронный ресурс]. — Режим доступа: <http://shishkova.ru/students/typology.htm>
10. Туйбаева Л. И. Использование интерактивных средств в обучении
11. средств [Электронный ресурс]. — Режим доступа: [https://sibac.info/conf](https://sibac.info/conf/26037)
12. /pedagog/x/26037
13. Улухужаев Н. З. Учебно-методический комплекс подготовки учителей начальных классов [Электронный ресурс] / Н. З. Улухужаев, М. О. Хамидова // Молодой ученый. — 2014. — №19. — С. 618-619. — Режим доступа: <https://moluch.ru/archive/78/13222>
14. Федеральные государственные образовательные стандарты общего
15. образования изменения [Электронный ресурс]. — Введ. 29.12.2014. — Режим
16. доступа: <https://xn--80abucjiibhv9a.xn-p1ai>(дата обращения: 14.03.2018).

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000